

Sextortion and Female Entrepreneurship¹

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Abstract

Sextortion is a sexualised form of corruption in which public officials demand sexual favours rather than cash bribes. The literature on sextortion indicates that women are more at risk of this form of corruption than men. We argue that this gendered form of corruption is likely to deter women from starting a business. Using data from the Global Corruption Barometer (GCB) and the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM), we show that the rate of sextortion in a country is associated with reductions in early-stage entrepreneurial activities, but only for women. There is no association between sextortion and male entrepreneurial activity. We further find that only opportunity-based entrepreneurship is deterred, indicating that sextortion undermines innovation and may be an endured and terrible reality for many necessity-driven female entrepreneurs around the world.

Keywords : sextortion, sexual corruption, entrepreneurship, female entrepreneurship, corruption, gender, entrepreneurial activity

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1. Introduction

Sextortion has been defined as “*the abuse of power to obtain a sexual benefit or advantage*” (IAWJ, 2012, p. 5). It is a modality of corruption - the abuse of entrusted power for private gain. In the case of sextortion, the private gain is any form of sex or coerced sexual gratification (such as demanding intimate images). Rather than the exchange being financial or related to other types of private gain (bribery, embezzlement, nepotism, etc.), it is of a sexual nature.⁷

Sextortion has many negative impacts on society at large, and on the individual victims. Most immediately, sextortion has severe negative physical and psychological impacts on the victims, such as high chances of sexually transmitted diseases, unwanted pregnancies, and multiple mental health issues (Gitlin, 2015). Studies have shown that sextortion disproportionately affects women and vulnerable people (Duri, 2020; Stahl, 2021; Merkle et al., 2017). Like other forms of corruption, sextortion distorts the economic, political, and institutional structure of a state. Yet, sextortion remains an understudied modality of corruption, partly due to the complicated nexus between sexual abuse and corruption; the reluctance of victims to discuss or report it due to the negative stigma attached to it; and the lack of adequate legal frameworks and judicial systems that can protect victims and punish perpetrators (Eldén et al. 2020; Feigenblat, 2020; Stahl, 2021; UNODC, 2020).

This paper contributes to the emerging academic literature on sextortion as a form of corruption by examining its impact on entrepreneurship. This follows scholarly calls to study the interplay of corruption within the informal and formal sectors of entrepreneurship (Bruton et al., 2021). We draw upon institutional theory and key critical research on entrepreneurial intentions and motivation to explore the effects of sextortion on entrepreneurial activity. While many empirical studies on sextortion have been concentrated on specific sectors, such as the

⁷ Sextortion is also a term that is used to define a situation whereby an individual threatens to distribute a victim’s intimate images, videos, or information unless they comply with the perpetrator’s demands (Gámez-Guadix et al., 2022; Patchin & Hinduja, 2020). This form of sextortion lies outside the scope of this study. This study relates to sextortion as sexual corruption only.

Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) sector, or on specific countries, (KEWASNET and ANEW, 2020; Merkle et al., 2023; Pommells et al., 2018), this paper makes use of country-level sextortion data collected in Europe, Asia, and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) between 2019 and 2021 as part of Transparency International's Global Corruption Barometer, as well as individual-level data on 49,000 individuals from the Global Entrepreneurial Monitor (GEM) 2018 Adult Population Survey (APS).

This study makes a number of important contributions to the literature. First, it advances our theoretical understanding of how sextortion influences the decision to engage in an entrepreneurial career, by applying Institutional Theory to this modality of corruption and integrating this variable into models of entrepreneurial intention and motivation. Second, we find that sextortion has a limiting effect on entrepreneurship, but only for women. While holding many variables that can influence entrepreneurial activities constant — such as age, unemployment, educational attainment, GDP per capita, corruption, democracy, ease of starting a business, women's economic participation and opportunity, trade openness, different cultural dimensions, and regions/different rounds of GCB survey — we find that sextortion reduces the entrepreneurial activities of early-stage female entrepreneurs, with no significant reduction for male entrepreneurs. As such, this study assists in the growth of more gender-specific information and theorization which could help to support and protect female entrepreneurs in their pursuit of fair and safe working environments. The third contribution of this study is the examination of sextortion on types of entrepreneurship. Our findings indicate that sextortion only reduces the entrepreneurial activities of women driven by opportunity as opposed to those pursuing entrepreneurship because they have no other job options (necessity entrepreneurship). To date, there has been no examination of the effect of sextortion on the motivations or behaviour of different types of entrepreneurs, thus this paper crucially highlights

an important gap in our understanding of the barriers to female-led entrepreneurship and innovation driven economic growth.

In the following sections, we present an overview of sextortion and examine its prevalence and consequences on a personal and societal level. Next, we set the foundation of our theoretical argument and present our hypotheses that relate sextortion to the rates and types of entrepreneurship. We then present our data analysis and methodology, followed by a discussion of the results. We discuss policy implications and draw a number of conclusions. Finally, we analyse the limitations of this study and make suggestions for future research.

2. Literature and Hypotheses

2.1 Sextortion as a form of Corruption

While a relatively new term and area of research exploration, sextortion is as old as other types of sexual violence and corruption (Feigenblatt, 2020). The term “sextortion” was coined by the International Association of Women Judges (IAWJ) during their three-year programme on “Stopping the Abuse of Power through Sexual Exploitation: Naming, Shaming, and Ending Sextortion”. To distinguish sextortion from other forms of corruption and sexual violence, the IAWJ (2012, p. 9) states that any sexually abusive conduct that has both a *sexual* and a *corruption component* most likely qualifies. Yet it is still complex to classify and fight sextortion in the judicial system due to the seemingly consensual exchange that takes place. This is exacerbated by the perception that victims are usually seen as “potential accomplices of [the] criminal act” (Eldén et al., 2020, p. 12), which can further dissuade victims from reporting cases of sextortion. However, the imbalance of power within the context of sextortion classifies it as a form of sexual violence due to the “element of coercion which may range from physical force to psychological intimidation, blackmail or other threats” (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022, p. 36).

Categorising sextortion as corruption due to the power dynamic inherent also helps to differentiate sextortion from “transactional sex” (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022, p. 47). Feigenblatt (2020) notes the following features of sextortion that generally qualify it as corruption.

1. Abuse of authority: The perpetrator uses the power entrusted to them for personal benefit.
2. Quid pro quo or “this-for-that”: The perpetrator demands or accepts a sexual favour in exchange for a benefit that they are empowered to withhold or confer.
3. Psychological coercion: Sextortion relies on coercive pressure rather than physical violence to obtain sexual favours. The imbalance of power between the perpetrator and the victim/survivor allows the perpetrator to exert the coercive pressure.

(Feigenblatt, 2020, p. 8)

Like other forms of corruption, sextortion is facilitated by resource inequality and power disparities, with sex as the currency (Bjarnegård et al., 2024). Studies show that a lack of basic amenities, especially in developing countries, enhances sextortion (KEWASNET & ANEW, 2020; Merkle et al., 2022; Merkle et al., 2023; Pommells et al., 2018). For instance, a study by the Kenya Water and Sanitation Civil Society Network (KEWASNET) and the African Civil Society Network on Water and Sanitation (ANEW) shows that sex has been used to access more favourable outcomes in the water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) sector in Kenya (2020). This trend has also been noted in Bangladesh (Merkle et al., 2022) and in East African countries like Rwanda, Tanzania, and Uganda (Pommells et al., 2018). However, while (perceptions of) corruption strongly predicts higher rates of sextortion across countries, likely

reflecting accountability gaps and the power of informal networks, factors such as economic development, press freedom, democracy, and women in parliament do not (Aja-Eke et al., 2023).

At the individual level, the risk of sextortion is exacerbated by limited financial means, limited legal options, bureaucratic processes, level of education, power dynamics, patriarchal structure, and gender-based and cultural norms (Chêne et al., 2010; Kubbe & Merkle, 2022; Merkle et al., 2017; Pommells et al., 2018; Sundström & Wängnerud, 2021). In particular, the patriarchal structure of most societies facilitates sextortion, due to power dynamics and the fact that most of the influential positions of authority are held by men.

2.2 The Victims and Costs of Sextortion

Though the empirical literature on sextortion is still in its early stages, sextortion has been noted in a wide number of industries and geographical regions. Sextortion is common in vulnerable communities and groups, and where there are significant power inequalities. For example, there have been reports of sextortion among refugees, and within the education system (Feigenblatt, 2020; Gitlin, 2015). Feigenblatt (2020) also cites appalling cases within migration, judicial systems, police, and public-sector employment (Hlongwane, 2017). It has become worryingly “normalized and institutionalized” across some countries and sectors (Eldén et al., 2020, p. 12). Syria, Libya, and Nigeria have been identified as displaying a high level of institutionalized sextortion, especially within forced and voluntary migration (Merkle et al., 2017), as well as Tanzania and Colombia, particularly in the educational sector (Eldén et al., 2020).

Sextortion disproportionately affects women (Chêne et al., 2010; Igwe, 2022; Merkle, 2022) and vulnerable people such as migrants and children (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022; Feigenblatt, 2020; Hendry, 2021; Merkle et al., 2017). While the study of Pommells et al.

(2018) focused on “mainstream” gender violence in the WASH sector, the study shows that the asymmetric relationship between males and females influences their access to basic amenities and exposes women to higher rates of sextortion. Due to the economic disparity between men and women, women may be “coerced into providing sex or sexual favours in an effort to either gain access to water or advance their position in a water queue” (Pommells et al., 2018, p. 1857). These findings align with the findings of Eldén et al. (2020, p. 12-13), which show that corruption has been so institutionalised in Colombia that “women were expected to pay with their bodies what men might be able to pay with money.” This is sometimes referred to as the “if no money then sex” scenario. However, women are also more at risk of paying with *both* sex and money (or other non-sexual benefits); referred to as the double cost of sextortion (Merkle et al., 2017; Stahl, 2021). When exploring the phenomenon of sextortion, social groups and families play a clear role, as the patriarchal structure of sextortion also “translates into families or relationships where women and girls are used to ‘pay’ for the bribes male relatives cannot afford” (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022, p. 38). It also spreads the widespread norm of female inferiority to men, to the extent that other women, including close female relatives of victims, become complicit in sextortion and the general patriarchal structure, just like other types of gender violence (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022).

The ill effects of sextortion are enormous, with many individual and national-level consequences. Sextortion widens gender gaps, which further affects the economic, political, and institutional structure of a state (Stahl, 2021; Pommells et al., 2018). It also has tremendous impacts on the victims, such as sexually transmitted diseases, unwanted pregnancies, psychological harm, and mental health issues, as well as a host of other grievous mental, physical, and emotional issues (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022; Duri, 2020; Gitlin, 2015; **Hlongwane, 2017**; Merkle et al., 2017; Stahl, 2021; Sundström & Wängnerud, 2021).

2.3 Hypotheses Development

This study examines the effects of sextortion on the entrepreneurial behaviours of female entrepreneurs, by drawing from the entrepreneurial intentions (EI) to entrepreneurial behaviour (EB) relationship, and Institutional Theory. The perceived threat of corruption negatively affects entrepreneurial intention to start businesses (Allini et al., 2017). We propose that females will be more acutely aware of this risk and will avoid entrepreneurial activities as a result.

Many studies in the entrepreneurship domain focus on understanding the factors affecting the *intention* to engage in entrepreneurial behaviours, and the predictive strength of intentions to future entrepreneurial *activity* (Kautonen et al., 2015; Virasa et al., 2022). Key theories that consider EI are the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) and Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event (SEE) model (Shapero & Sokol, 1982). TPB holds that the intention to become an entrepreneur and the subsequent actions taken by the entrepreneur are the result of socialisation processes in which personal subjective perceptions, attraction to entrepreneurship, and perceived behavioural control are necessary contributors (Ajzen, 1991, 2020)⁸. Thus, an individual's favourable or unfavourable appraisal of the specified behaviour will affect their intention to pursue it, as determined by his/her underlying beliefs about the likely outcome of that behaviour, or the relative costs arising (Ajzen, 1991; Zellweger et al., 2011). Perceived behavioural control is composed of an individual's self-efficacy, or "perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behavior of interests" (Ajzen, 1991, p. 183), and the extent to which the individual can control the performance or behaviour (Kruse

⁸ Subjective norms, linked to the normative belief system, refer to the perceived social pressure exerted by others, to perform the target behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) is also a factor theorised within TPB. However, this factor has not been as consistently shown within EI-EB studies (Carsrud & Brannback, 2011; Maes et al., 2014).

et al., 2021). The SEE view on entrepreneurial intentions considers that founder intention is formed due to individual perceptions of the desirability (personal attractiveness) of starting a business, feasibility (capability and controllability) of starting a business, and a third component ‘propensity to act’ – a disposition to act on decisions, perhaps due to a trigger which displaces an individual’s career or life inertia (Krueger et al., 2000). Both models have shown usefulness in predicting entrepreneurial intentions, despite limited direct effect relationships of social/subjective norms in TPB (Krueger et al., 2000, Maes et al., 2014). Both assume a predetermination of behavioural beliefs (“if I do this, Y will happen”), and both viewpoints align with considerations of self-efficacy. In studying the desirability and feasibility factors underpinning EI (using SEE), Fitzsimmons and Douglas (2011) noted a regulatory interaction effect wherein individuals either seek goal accomplishment (promotion), or safety and the avoidance of negative outcomes (prevention). We consider that prospective entrepreneurs who perceive the risk of sextortion may align more with preventative considerations, thus reduce their perceptions of desirability and feasibility for new venture creation. Essentially, starting a business in a context which has a high rate of sexual corruption would be a terrible prospect for an entrepreneur, which they will try to avoid (unless in desperation).

The institution-based view suggests that a firm’s strategic choices are not entirely driven by industry conditions and firm-specific resources (Barney, 1991), but also by the formal and informal conditions embedded within a firm (Scott, 1995). Thus, institutional factors, such as the presence of corruption within a system, impinge upon the strategic actions of an entrepreneur or firm (Ahmed & Brennan, 2019), by reinforcing or attenuating one’s assumptions of potential success. Corruption has been highlighted as a key institutional factor in determining the success of entrepreneurship endeavour (Anokhin & Schulze, 2009). When corruption becomes entrenched in the normalised business practices of a country, these working conditions provide cues for prospective entrepreneurs considering the career. As

stated, we propose that entrepreneurs will consider contexts where sextortion and sex-based corruption are heightened, to be less desirable to start a business. The barriers to business creation for females have been noted to take many forms; institutional, familial and societal among others. Females face challenges in forming effective business networks (McAdam et al., 2018), and accessing funding (Lins & Lutz 2016). Many face challenges due to cultural and religious contexts which limit entry to the career (Naguib & Jamali, 2009). Maes et al. (2014) noted that levels of perceived behavioural control for females were significantly affected by their perceived control over external events (e.g. legislation), while males were not. In light of heightened risk of sextortion for females, we consider it is a key deterrent to prospective female entrepreneurs, resulting in a lower rate of female entrepreneurial activity.

H1: The prevalence of sextortion deters women from entrepreneurial activities.

While intention-based models provide strong direction for our understanding of entrepreneurial behaviour (Krueger et al., 2000), they do not explain fully why individuals choose to launch a business. In fact, explained variance for the EI to EB relationship have ranged between 10% to 37% in various empirical studies (Belchior & Lyons, 2021). It is suggested that we should consider the interplay between entrepreneurial intentions and key motivations to provide additional insight (Carsrud & Brännback 2011). Motivational factors may further augment our context-specific understanding of entrepreneurial activity. For example, Douglas et al. (2021) considers that EI models limit our holistic understanding of the entrepreneur as they conflate two key intention-based questions (“do you want to be an entrepreneur”) and (“what type/for what outcomes”), which may limit our understanding of key motivational cues. There are many, varied, and context-dependent motivations for new business creation, which may affect the way these subsequent ventures will emerge and be managed (Westhead et al., 2005; Edelman et al., 2010; Murnieks et al., 2020; Belchior & Lyons, 2022). Some divide entrepreneurial motivational factors into intrinsic and extrinsic

conditions (Shaver et al., 2001; Murnieks et al., 2020), where intrinsic motivation stems from a person's interest in the entrepreneurial task or a sense of self-actualisation, and extrinsic motivation relates to the external reward associated with the career (Carsrud & Brännback, 2011).

Two main typologies of entrepreneur are discussed based on these drivers (Reynolds et al. 2002): opportunity-driven entrepreneurship and necessity-driven entrepreneurship, noting a difference between those who are pulled to entrepreneurship by opportunity, desired independence, exploration or lucrative potential, and those “pushed” to entrepreneurship out of necessity or limited alternatives, as a mode of survival, or to sustain an income. Countries with a high relative prevalence of improvement-driven (opportunity) entrepreneurship over necessity entrepreneurship appear to be primarily innovation-driven countries (Bosma & Kelly, 2019; GEM, 2023). In these countries, opportunities may be more abundant, and individuals may have more alternatives to make a living. Therefore, there is a positive correlation between opportunity-led entrepreneurial activity and GDP per capita while necessity entrepreneurship shows the opposite association (GEM, 2023).

We predict that sextortion may reduce the amount of opportunity entrepreneurs, but necessity entrepreneurs may not be able to find alternative career options to starting a business. Audretsch et al. (2022) studied the effect that tax rate, corruption and government expenditure changes could have on the allocation of necessity and opportunity entrepreneurs across 52 countries, noting that corruption's negative effect on opportunity entrepreneurship is twice as strong as its effect on necessity entrepreneurship, demonstrating that opportunity entrepreneurship is more significantly affected by corruption. We contend that contextually, there will be a difference noted between opportunity- and necessity-based entrepreneurs in how they respond to a climate of sextortion. Given their usual reduced access to resources and supportive institutions, as well as their greater potential exposure to extortion and corruption

(Mallon & Fainschmidt, 2022), we suggest that necessity entrepreneurs have fewer options to leave or switch careers, thus will be less likely to reduce their entrepreneurial behaviour as compared to opportunity entrepreneurs.

H2: Sextortion, as a form of corruption, will have a greater negative effect on opportunity-driven entrepreneurship than necessity-driven entrepreneurship.

3. Data and Methodology

This paper makes use of data from the Global Corruption Barometer (GCB) and the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) to study the impacts of sextortion on early-stage entrepreneurial activities. The GCB collects data on experienced and perceptual corruption in different countries around the world. We make use of the most recent GCB surveys which contained sextortion questions. These were carried out for the European Union (EU) (2021), Asia (2020), the Pacific (2021), the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) (2019), and Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) (2019). The list of countries used in our analysis is presented in Table A1 (in the Appendix). Due to missing data for our control variables, we lose the MENA and Pacific countries from our sample. The average rate of people who state that they have experienced or know someone who has experienced sextortion in the sample used in this study is 10.4% with Japan having the lowest rate (2%) and Brazil and Peru having the highest rate (20%).

There are slight differences in the phrasing of the questions in each of the regions. However, the question on sextortion used in this paper generally refers to individuals affirming that they have been or known someone that has been exploited sexually or asked for sexual favours in exchange for a service and/or benefit, by someone in a position of authority. More details on the questions for different regions can be found in Table A3 (in the Appendix).

Therefore, sextortion as used in this paper is the percentage of people that have either experienced sextortion or know someone that has experienced sextortion in their country.

GEM's research has produced almost 30 years of data on rates of entrepreneurship across multiple phases of the entrepreneurial process. The data is used to create national and regional reports, global reports, and special issues on themes such as women entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship education and social entrepreneurship, as well as hundreds of peer-reviewed research publications. As part of this research, the Adult Population Survey (APS) is a comprehensive questionnaire, administered to a minimum of 2000 adults in each GEM country, designed to collect detailed information on respondents' entrepreneurial activity (formal and informal), attitudes, and aspirations. Our study centres on entrepreneurial activities using the 2018 dataset (160'000 adults across 49 economies), with an emphasis on observing the differences between men and women.

Early-stage entrepreneurial activities (ESEA) captures if a participant between the age of 18 to 64 is involved in Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity. Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) is a term that has been created by the GEM consortium to denote entrepreneurial activity that is centred on the period preceding and immediately after the actual start of a firm. Hence, it includes the phases of (i) nascent entrepreneurship when an entrepreneur is actively involved in setting up a business, and (ii) new business ownership, owning and managing a business in existence up to 42 months. It is a dichotomous variable, with a value of 1 indicating that the participant is involved in ESEA and 0 indicating that the participant is not.

We are also interested in examining the impacts of sextortion on two different categories of early stage-entrepreneurs. **Opportunity ESEA** captures if a participant between the age of 18 to 64 is involved in opportunity early-stage entrepreneurial activity. It is a dichotomous variable, with a value of 1 indicating that the participant is involved in opportunity ESEA and

0 indicating that the participant is not. **Necessity ESEA** captures if a participant between the age of 18 to 64 is involved in necessity early-stage entrepreneurial activity. It is a dichotomous variable, with a value of 1 indicating that the participant is involved in necessity ESEA and 0 indicating that the participant is not.

We also control for other individual and country level factors that may be correlated with both entrepreneurial activity and the prevalence of sextortion; age (Zhang & Acs, 2018), unemployment (Cowling & Bygrave, 2003), educational attainment (Millan et al., 2014), corruption (Allini et al., 2017), GDP per Capita, democracy (Audretsch & Moog, 2022), ease of starting a business, women's economic participation and opportunity, cultural factors (Haggard & Haggard, 2018), and trade openness (Lobont et al., 2023).

Age, employment status, and educational attainment were derived from the GEM data. We made use of a binary variable for employment status with "1" representing unemployed and "0" representing "employed" participants. We created a dummy variable for the different categories of educational attainment for each of the participants from the GEM data. The original data from the GEM APS captured 9 different categories of education using the UN's harmonized educational attainment (as updated in 2018). We also used GDP per capita from the World Development Indicators (WDI) of the World Bank (2020). We also included the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) as a proxy for the overall level of corruption in a country.⁹

Additionally, we included democracy (from Polity V data), ease of starting business (from the sub-index of the World Bank's Ease of Doing Business rankings for the year 2018), and women's economic participation and opportunity (from the sub-index of World Economic Forum's Gender Gap Index 2021) in our models. We also included trade openness from the Penn World Tables. This data sums the exports and imports of a participant's country as a share of the country's GDP. We also include measures of cultural dimensions from Hofstede's

⁹ Our results are robust to excluding the CPI from our models.

Cultural Dimensions which identifies 6 dimensions of a society's culture: individualism, power, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, long-term orientation and indulgence. We also include dummy variables for the different regions, to account for region/round-specific factors, including the fact that the sextortion question phrasing varies slightly. More details on all the variables used in the analysis can be found in Table A2 (in the Appendix).

To examine the relationship between sextortion and entrepreneurship, we estimate probit models of the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Pr (ESEA_{ij} = 1) &= \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 SEX_j + \beta_2 GEN_i + \beta_3 AGE_i + \beta_4 UNEMP_i + \beta_5 EDU_i \\
 &+ \beta_6 GDP_j + \beta_7 CORR_j + \beta_8 DEM_j + \beta_9 BUS_j + \beta_{10} WOECO_j + \beta_{11} TO_j \\
 &+ \beta_{12} CUL_j + \beta_{13} REGDum_j + \beta_{14} REG_j)
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Full Samples					Women					Men				
	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ESEA	49163	0.119	0.324	0	1	26322	0.103	0.304	0	1	22841	0.137	0.344	0	1
Opportunity ESEA	49163	0.08	0.272	0	1	26322	0.066	0.248	0	1	22841	0.097	0.296	0	1
Necessity ESEA	49163	0.032	0.176	0	1	26322	0.031	0.174	0	1	22841	0.033	0.178	0	1
Sextortion	49163	10.446	4.536	2	20	26322	10.624	4.529	2	20	22841	10.241	4.536	2	20
Gender (Female)	49163	0.535	0.499	0	1	26322	1	0	1	1	22841	0	0	0	0
Age	49163	44.548	15.623	18	94	26322	44.95	15.407	18	94	22841	44.085	15.856	18	94
Unemployment	49163	0.198	0.399	0	1	26322	0.217	0.412	0	1	22841	0.177	0.382	0	1
Bachelor or equivalent	49163	0.151	0.358	0	1	26322	0.143	0.35	0	1	22841	0.161	0.367	0	1
Doctor or equivalent	49163	0.004	0.063	0	1	26322	0.003	0.057	0	1	22841	0.005	0.07	0	1
Lower Secondary or Second Stage Basic Education	49163	0.176	0.381	0	1	26322	0.178	0.383	0	1	22841	0.173	0.379	0	1
Master or equivalent	49163	0.047	0.211	0	1	26322	0.044	0.205	0	1	22841	0.049	0.217	0	1
Post-Secondary or Second Stage of Basic Education	49163	0.105	0.307	0	1	26322	0.108	0.31	0	1	22841	0.102	0.303	0	1
Post-Secondary Non-Tertiary Education	49163	0.026	0.159	0	1	26322	0.028	0.165	0	1	22841	0.023	0.151	0	1
Pre-Primary Education	49163	0.119	0.324	0	1	26322	0.132	0.338	0	1	22841	0.105	0.306	0	1
Short-Cycle Tertiary Education	49163	0.027	0.162	0	1	26322	0.028	0.164	0	1	22841	0.026	0.159	0	1
GDP per capita (log) – Constant 2015 US Dollars	49163	9.723	0.833	7.502	11.274	26322	9.685	0.85	7.502	11.274	22841	9.767	0.81	7.502	11.274
Corruption	49163	41.809	14.079	15	64	26322	42.242	14.047	15	64	22841	41.309	14.1	15	64
Democracy	49163	8.925	3.308	-7	10	26322	8.887	3.357	-7	10	22841	8.968	3.25	-7	10
Ease of Starting a Business	49163	84.897	5.939	64.79	94.675	26322	84.789	6.066	64.79	94.675	22841	85.021	5.787	64.79	94.675
Women Economic Participation & Opportunity	49163	66.867	9.273	32.6	81	26322	66.515	9.634	32.6	81	22841	67.274	8.821	32.6	81
Trade Openness	49163	78.721	39.329	24.12	209.385	26322	77.307	39.152	24.12	209.385	22841	80.35	39.47	24.12	209.385
Power Distance Index	49163	59.329	17.212	11	104	26322	59.669	16.955	11	104	22841	58.937	17.496	11	104
Individualism vs Collectivism	49163	45.829	18.571	13	80	26322	45.193	18.578	13	80	22841	46.562	18.536	13	80
Masculinity vs Femininity	49163	49.681	20.369	5	110	26322	49.357	20.081	5	110	22841	50.054	20.69	5	110
Uncertainty Avoidance Index	49163	74.083	19.621	29	112	26322	74.1	19.786	29	112	22841	74.064	19.429	29	112
Long Term vs Short Term Normative Orientation	49163	52.657	18.651	13	100	26322	51.708	18.349	13	100	22841	53.75	18.935	13	100
Indulgence vs Restraint	49163	44.678	16.153	16	83	26322	45.135	16.248	16	83	22841	44.151	16.027	16	83
EU	49163	0.674	0.469	0	1	26322	0.65	0.477	0	1	22841	0.701	0.458	0	1
LAC	49163	0.177	0.382	0	1	26322	0.191	0.393	0	1	22841	0.161	0.368	0	1

Reference for educational levels: (Upper) Secondary Education

Reference for regions: Asia

Where $ESEA_{ij}$ captures the early-stage entrepreneurial activity of individual I in country j , SEX_j is the rate of sextortion in country j , GEN_i is a dummy that takes a value of 1 if the respondent is female, AGE_i is age, $UNEMP_i$ takes a value of 1 if the respondent is unemployed, EDU_i captures educational attainment, GDP_j is GDP per capita, $CORR_j$ is corruption, DEM_j is democracy, BUS_j is ease of starting a business, $WOECO_j$ is women's economic opportunity and participation, TO_j is trade openness, CUL_j captures cultural dimensions, and REG_j is a set of dummies capturing the region that the survey was carried out in. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the individual level variables used in this paper. More details on the countries and sample size of each country used can be found in Table A1 (in the appendix).

4. Results

Table 2 examines the relationship between sextortion and entrepreneurial activity. We begin by looking at overall ESEA. Column 1 pools both men and women and finds that a one standard deviation increase in sextortion (4.5%) reduces entrepreneurial activities by about 1.4%. This is a meaningful change relative to the mean of ESEA which is about 12%. As noted above, women are more at risk of sextortion. Column 2 restricts the sample to only women, and we obtain a larger estimated marginal effect. However, in Column 3 we find no significant association between sextortion and male entrepreneurial activities. These findings are in line with our theoretical predictions – women are more at risk of sextortion, an act that entails significant and ongoing harm, and therefore are less likely to be involved in entrepreneurial activity as doing so would increase their exposure to predatory public officials.

Table 2: Sextortion and Early-Stage Entrepreneurial Activity (ESEA)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
	ESEA			Opportunity ESEA			Necessity ESEA		
	Full Sample	Women Only	Men Only	Full Sample	Women Only	Men Only	Full Sample	Women Only	Men Only
Sextortion	-0.003*** (0.001)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.001* (0.001)	-0.003** (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)
Gender (Female)	-0.032*** (0.003)			-0.025*** (0.002)			-0.003** (0.001)		
Age	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.001*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.000*** (0.000)	-0.000*** (0.000)	-0.000*** (0.000)
Unemployment	-0.064*** (0.003)	-0.057*** (0.003)	-0.073*** (0.004)	-0.054*** (0.002)	-0.045*** (0.002)	-0.065*** (0.003)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.004** (0.002)	0.000 (0.003)
Educational Level: (Upper) Secondary Education	REF								
Bachelor or equivalent	0.052*** (0.005)	0.049*** (0.007)	0.055*** (0.008)	0.044*** (0.004)	0.042*** (0.006)	0.047*** (0.006)	0.003 (0.002)	0.001 (0.003)	0.004 (0.003)
Doctor or equivalent	0.035 (0.026)	0.090* (0.046)	-0.006 (0.030)	0.040* (0.023)	0.073* (0.040)	0.017 (0.027)	-0.006 (0.011)	0.010 (0.022)	-0.016 (0.010)
Lower Secondary or Second Stage of Basic Education	-0.014*** (0.004)	-0.009* (0.005)	-0.020*** (0.006)	-0.015*** (0.003)	-0.010*** (0.004)	-0.021*** (0.005)	0.002 (0.002)	0.003 (0.003)	0.000 (0.003)
Master or equivalent	0.104*** (0.010)	0.108*** (0.014)	0.104*** (0.014)	0.083*** (0.008)	0.079*** (0.012)	0.091*** (0.013)	0.012** (0.005)	0.017** (0.007)	0.008 (0.006)
Post-Secondary Non-Tertiary Education	0.040*** (0.006)	0.027*** (0.007)	0.056*** (0.009)	0.032*** (0.005)	0.021*** (0.005)	0.047*** (0.008)	0.003 (0.003)	0.004 (0.003)	0.002 (0.004)
Pre-Primary Education	-0.038*** (0.007)	-0.028*** (0.008)	-0.051*** (0.011)	-0.033*** (0.005)	-0.022*** (0.006)	-0.048*** (0.008)	-0.001 (0.004)	-0.001 (0.005)	-0.001 (0.006)
Primary Education or First Stage of Basic Education	-0.027*** (0.004)	-0.019*** (0.005)	-0.039*** (0.007)	-0.023*** (0.003)	-0.014*** (0.004)	-0.036*** (0.005)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.000 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.004)
Short-Cycle Tertiary Education	-0.001 (0.008)	-0.001 (0.010)	-0.000 (0.013)	0.008 (0.006)	0.005 (0.008)	0.012 (0.011)	-0.008** (0.003)	-0.007* (0.004)	-0.008 (0.005)
GDP per capita (log) – Constant 2015 US Dollars	0.061*** (0.007)	0.053*** (0.009)	0.071*** (0.011)	0.035*** (0.005)	0.027*** (0.007)	0.046*** (0.009)	0.026*** (0.004)	0.023*** (0.005)	0.028*** (0.005)
Corruption	0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)
Democracy	-0.007*** (0.001)	-0.007*** (0.001)	-0.007*** (0.001)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.003*** (0.001)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)
Ease of Starting a Business	-0.005*** (0.001)	-0.005*** (0.001)	-0.005*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.003*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)
Women Economic Participation & Opportunity	-0.004*** (0.000)	-0.003*** (0.000)	-0.005*** (0.001)	-0.001*** (0.000)	-0.001** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)	-0.002*** (0.000)
Trade Openness	0.001***	0.000***	0.001***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000***

	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Power Distance Index	0.001***	0.001**	0.001***	0.000*	0.000	0.000**	0.000***	0.000***	0.000**
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Individualism vs Collectivism	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Masculinity vs Femininity	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.000***	-0.000***	-0.000**	-0.000***	-0.000***	-0.000***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Uncertainty Avoidance Index	0.001***	0.001***	0.001**	0.000***	0.000*	0.001***	0.000	0.000**	-0.000
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Long Term vs Short Term Normative Orientation	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.001***	-0.000**	-0.000***	-0.000**	-0.000***
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Indulgence vs Restraint	0.002***	0.001***	0.003***	0.001***	0.000	0.002***	0.000***	0.000***	0.000*
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Region: Asia	REF								
EU	-0.044***	-0.033***	-0.059***	-0.042***	-0.031***	-0.056***	-0.007	-0.006	-0.009
	(0.010)	(0.012)	(0.016)	(0.008)	(0.009)	(0.013)	(0.005)	(0.006)	(0.008)
LAC	-0.004	0.007	-0.023	-0.008	0.002	-0.024**	-0.002	-0.000	-0.006
	(0.011)	(0.015)	(0.016)	(0.008)	(0.011)	(0.012)	(0.006)	(0.008)	(0.008)
Observations	49,163	26,322	22,841	49,163	26,322	22,841	49,163	26,322	22,841

Note: Main entries are average marginal effects obtained from Probit Models

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The remaining columns test our hypothesis (H2) that women entrepreneurship of opportunity will be more strongly correlated with sextortion rates than necessity-based entrepreneurship. We find that this is indeed the case. For men, sextortion is not significantly or meaningfully correlated with either form of entrepreneurship (columns 6 and 9). However, the results in Column 5 indicate that a one standard deviation increase in sextortion reduces the likelihood that a women will engage in opportunity ESEA of women by about 1.4%. This is quite substantial, especially when compared with the mean of opportunity ESEA (8%). Finally, Column 8 suggests that the threat of sextortion does not deter necessity entrepreneurship for women. Accordingly, H2 is supported as we find that sextortion has a greater negative effect on opportunity-driven entrepreneurship than necessity-driven entrepreneurship.

5. Discussion

Sextortion is a type of sexual violence and corruption, which has a transactional element and an asymmetric balance of coercive power between the victim and perpetrator (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022). Sextortion is exacerbated by the lack of basic amenities and the socio-cultural and political dominance of men in most societies; it is also heightened by gender gaps and the power dynamics between men and women in various key sectors (Stahl, 2021; Pommells et al., 2018). While a widespread criminal act, there is scant literature on how the presence of sextortion in a region influences the formation of intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activity, or the rates and types of active entrepreneurs.

Studies suggest that the social context influences the feasibility and desirability of decisions to engage in a particular behaviour through collective views, expectations, and beliefs (Krueger et al., 2000). We apply probit models and data from the Global Corruption Barometer (GCB) and the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) to study the impacts of sextortion on early-stage entrepreneurial activities of women. We predict that sextortion lowers the likelihood of entrepreneurial activity due to the immense costs imposed on victims of this

heinous abuse of power. We further argue that the threat of sextortion poses a more significant disincentive to female entrepreneurs. This is consistent with the central thesis of institution-based view that institutions — regulative, normative, and cognitive institutions — can influence an individual through a series of incentives or disincentives that channel his or her behaviour to a particular direction (Friel, 2017; Scott, 1995).

Our results echo multiple studies in the field noting that being a woman significantly reduces one's entrepreneurial activities (GEM, 2023). Next, while holding gender and other variables that can influence entrepreneurial activities constant — such as age, unemployment, educational attainment, GDP per capita, corruption, democracy, ease of starting a business, women's economic participation and opportunity, trade openness, different cultural dimensions, and regions/rounds of GCB survey — sextortion reduces entrepreneurial activities. This becomes even more glaring when the sample of women is separated from the sample of men. For women, sextortion reduces entrepreneurial activities, including opportunity ESEA. However, for men, there is no significant impact of sextortion on the entrepreneurial activities in all the models. As sextortion disproportionately affects women (Chêne et al., 2010; Igwe, 2022; Merkle, 2022), this implies that the threat of sextortion affects the entrepreneurial behaviours of female founders more than males.

To shed some light on the types of entrepreneurs which may be affected by sextortion, we explore entrepreneurial motivations (Krueger & Brazeal, 1994; Shaver et al., 2001; Carsrud & Brannback, 2011). GEM (2005) developed two main typologies of entrepreneur based on their over-arching motivation to start a business, noting a difference between those who are pulled to entrepreneurship by opportunity and those who are pushed to entrepreneurship out of necessity. When we examine opportunity ESEA and necessity ESEA, we find that sextortion reduces the opportunity ESEA for women, but there is no significant effect of sextortion on opportunity ESEA for men. Sextortion does not have any significant effects on the necessity

ESEA in the full sample, or for the male or female groupings. Thus, sextortion has a greater negative effect on opportunity-driven entrepreneurship than necessity-driven entrepreneurship. Furthermore, while sextortion does not significantly influence necessity ESEA, being a woman impacts necessity ESEA negatively.

6. Limitations and Implications for Future Research

While we believe that our study is the first to examine the role of sextortion in shaping female entrepreneurial activity, it is not without its limitations. Firstly, we acknowledge that we are limited to cross sectional data that precludes us from including either country or individual fixed effects. Longitudinal research designs could provide better insights into the dynamics of the association between sextortion and entrepreneurial activity. In addition, while we control for several important social, political, and economic factors, including aggregate cultural dimensions, countries, and regions within countries, vary in important ways. Therefore, qualitative work is needed. This may provide a deeper understanding of the behaviours and institutions at play. Qualitative and experiential work is also needed to develop effective anti-sextortion policies to address the issue that we have identified in our study. In particular, the fact that sextortion does not predict a change in the likelihood of a woman becoming an entrepreneur of necessity, who are likely amongst the poorest in any country, points to the need for targeted anti-sextortion policies.

While the GCB surveys are carried out to a high standard and ask about people's direct experience or knowledge of sextortion, obtaining data pertaining to tangible experiences or incidence of any form of corruption is challenging (Goel & Nelson, 2021). We note that given the nuanced and sensitive nature of the topic, mixed methods and qualitative explorations of sextortion in entrepreneurship would assist in bringing new dimensions to the fore. As stated in our paper, sextortion is normalised in some societies, and feeds into power asymmetries, patriarchal structures, themes of female inferiority, and problematic family decision-making

based on institutional and educational failures (Bicker Caarten et al., 2022). While our study finds that there is a link between sextortion and entrepreneurial activity, more work is needed to explore the specific ways that cues relating to sextortion are accessed and assimilated by the nascent female founders.

We call for research at multiple levels. At the individual level, the psychology of the entrepreneur could be probed in their decision-making surrounding the challenge of sextortion. Entrepreneurs, like most individuals, have value-systems, which are challenged negatively when faced with situations or systems which are incongruous (Conger, 2012). These values are trans-situational, enduring standards by which entrepreneurs judge the desirability and relative importance of their actions, with respect to their welfare and that of others. Faced with a situation of sextortion, an entrepreneur's values and belief systems are worthy of study, as are the perceptions and attitudes of the social actors surrounding them.

In entrepreneurship research, institutional or national corruption has been noted to both positively and negatively affect business creation. Anokhin and Schulze (2009, p. 466) suggested that corruption may be the '*missing variable*' in explaining relationships between entrepreneurship, innovation, and economic prosperity. Corruption can harm the economy and growth rate of a country by "*sanding the wheel*" of entrepreneurship, even when a country's business climate is poor (Dutta & Sobel, 2016). However, corruption via bribery is sometimes argued to help entrepreneurs overcome excessive administrative procedures and controls (the "*grease the wheel*" effect) (Zhou & Peng, 2012), a point which motivates individuals towards entrepreneurship in highly corrupt economic systems and bureaucracies (Ceresia & Mendola, 2019). While such arguments often neglect the fact that excessive red tape is a product of corruption in that it is designed to be inefficient in order to incentivise and extract bribes, (Breen and Gillanders, 2012), more research is needed to explore whether there is a similar

process at play in relation to sextortion in navigating certain industry or administrative processes, especially given the risk and experiences for those affected.

7. Implications for Practice

Adequate anti-corruption laws and sexual offence laws, or preferably, a fusion thereof that specifically targets sextortion, must be enacted to fight sextortion, encourage entrepreneurship, and protect women, particularly those for who entrepreneurship is not a choice but a necessity. Efforts need to be taken to address the seriousness of sextortion in relation to its portrayal in education, media, and popular culture (Druganova et al., 2023). Additionally, deliberate efforts to identify and distinguish sextortion from other types of corruption and sexual abuse are imperative, especially in the legal system (Feigenblatt, 2020, p. 26).

Our study findings point to a clear business cost for countries who fail to respond to the threat of pervasive sextortion. If institutions define “the rules of the game in a society” (North, 1990, p. 3), providing the regulative, normative, and cognitive structures and activities that dictate behaviour (Scott, 1995, p. 33), then it is up to those developing the requisite rules to act accordingly. Social contexts with higher levels of generalized trust, cooperative norms, and lower transaction costs increase start-up intentions (Amini Sedeh et al., 2020). To bolster entrepreneurship in a country, governments can assist by supporting the shared interest of public and private parties in their commercial entrepreneurial pursuits (Bruton et al., 2021). By investing in economic affairs and increasing social security, governments can support and protect women engaged in necessity entrepreneurship in particular (Audretsch et al., 2022). Anti-corruption policy is pro-growth and pro-women policy

8. Conclusion

Most definitions of entrepreneurs include a reference to the burden of risk which is assumed by the individual — usually financial, psychic, and/or social (Hisrich et al., 2005, p. 8). However, in the context where sextortion may accompany the founding and operations of a new company, the cost is too high for female founders who have the luxury of free choice. Our results indicate that sextortion does not significantly influence the entrepreneurial activities of men who are early-stage entrepreneurs. Neither does it affect females who start their company motivated by necessity. Our findings indicate that sextortion only reduces the entrepreneurial activities of women driven by opportunity, who may opt away from their founding motivations to another career. To date, there has been no examination of the effect of sextortion on the motivations or behaviour of entrepreneurs, thus this paper crucially highlights this important gap in our understanding of the barriers to start-up for female founders globally. This study assists in the growth of more gender-specific information and theorization which could help to support and protect female entrepreneurs in their pursuit of fair and safe working environments.

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APPENDIX**Table A1.** Country Details and Sample Size

Country Code	Country	Region	Sample Size
ARG	Argentina	LAC	867
AUT	Austria	EU	1290
BGR	Bulgaria	EU	1971
BRA	Brazil	LAC	1141
CHL	Chile	LAC	4486
CHN	China	Asia	1382
COL	Colombia	LAC	1038
DEU	Germany	EU	4150
ESP	Spain	EU	11089
FRA	France	EU	910
GRC	Greece	EU	1196
HRV	Croatia	EU	1981
IDN	Indonesia	Asia	1379
IND	India	Asia	2470
IRL	Ireland	EU	695
ITA	Italy	EU	2000
JPN	Japan	Asia	559
KOR	South Korea	Asia	540
NLD	Netherlands	EU	778
PER	Peru	LAC	1186
POL	Poland	EU	2963
SVK	Slovakia	EU	1613

SVN	Slovenia	EU	742
SWE	Sweden	EU	1734
THA	Thailand	Asia	1003

Min – South Korea (540), Maximum Spain (11,089)

EU – European region; LAC – Latin America and the Caribbean

Table A2. Definition and Sources of Variables

Variables	Definitions	Sources and year of data
Sextortion	The percentage of people that have either experienced sextortion or know someone that has experienced sextortion	Transparency International's Global Corruption Barometer (GCB), 2019-2021. LAC – 2019 Asia – 2020 EU - 2021
Early-Stage Entrepreneurial Activity (ESEA)	Combines the stage in advance of the start of a new firm (nascent entrepreneurship) and the stage directly after the start of a new firm (owning-managing a new firm). Items: 1) Are you, alone or with others, currently trying to start a new business, including any self-employment or selling any goods or services to others? 2) Are you, alone or with others, currently trying to start a new business or a new venture for your employer as part of your normal work?	Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) 2018 Adult Population

		Survey (APS) Global Individual Level
Opportunity ESEA	Opportunity-driven early-stage entrepreneur. Based on item: Which one of the following, do you feel, is the most important motive for pursuing this opportunity?	Data
Necessity ESEA	Necessity-driven early-stage entrepreneur [As per item above]	
Gender (Female)	The gender of the participants recoded as “1” for females and “0” for men.	
Age	Age of the participant, participants are between 18 to 64 years old.	
Unemployment	The employment status of the participants, recoded with “0” representing employed and “1” representing “unemployed” participants	
Educational Attainment	We created a dummy variable for the different categories of educational attainment for each of the participants from the GEM data. The GEM APS data capture 9 different categories of education using the UN’s harmonized educational attainment as updated in 2018. The	

	9 different categories of educational attainment are: pre-primary education, primary education or first stage of basic education, lower secondary or second stage of basic education, (upper) secondary education, post-secondary non-tertiary education, short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor or equivalent, master or equivalent, doctor or equivalent	
GDP Per Capita	GDP per Capita in constant 2015 US Dollars	WDI, World Bank (2020)
Corruption	Corruption Perception Index. Takes values between 0 and 100 with 0 representing the lowest level of corruption perception and 100 representing the highest level of corruption.	Transparency International (2020)
Democracy	A quantitative measure of democratic and autocratic regimes with -10 representing full autocracy and 10 representing full democracy.	Polity V, Centre for Systemic Peace (2018)
Ease of starting a Business	A sub-index of World Bank's Ease of doing business. Scale: 0 to 100, with 100 representing the most business-friendly environment.	World Bank Ease of Doing Business (2018)
Women's	Subindex of the Gender Gap Index that	World Economic

Economic Participation and Opportunity	considers labour force participation rates, wage equality, earned income, and positions as legislators, senior officials and managers, and professional and technical workers. It is rescaled from 0-1 to 0-100 with 0 representing the worst score and 100 representing the best score.	Forum's Global Gender Gap Report (2021)
Trade Openness	The percentage of export and imports as a share of a country's GDP	Penn World Tables (2017)
Cultural Dimensions	<p>This contains 6 different variables that measure the cultural dimension and values of different countries from Hofstede's Cultural Dimension Matrix. The 6 different variables are:</p> <p>1. Power distance index: "Power Distance is the extent to which the less powerful members of organizations and institutions (like the family) accept and expect that power is distributed unequally" – the larger the number, the higher power distance</p> <p>2. Individualism vs collectivism:</p> <p>"Individualism is the extent to which people feel independent, as</p>	Hofstede's Cultural Dimension Matrix, 2015

	<p>opposed to being interdependent as members of larger wholes” – larger number, more individualist</p> <p>3. Masculinity vs femininity:</p> <p>“Masculinity is the extent to which the use of force is endorsed socially. In a masculine society, men are supposed to be tough” – larger number, more masculine</p> <p>4. Uncertainty avoidance index:</p> <p>“Uncertainty avoidance deals with a society’s tolerance for uncertainty and ambiguity” – larger number, more avoidance; lower number, more tolerant</p> <p>5. Long term orientation vs short term normative orientation: “Long-term orientation deals with change. In a long-time-oriented culture, the basic notion about the world is that it is in flux, and preparing for the future is always needed. In a short-time-oriented culture, the world is essentially as it was created, so that the past provides a moral compass, and adhering to it is morally good . . . this dimension</p>	
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	<p>predicts life philosophies, religiosity, and educational achievement – larger number, short term orientation</p> <p>6. Indulgence vs restraint larger number, indulgent: “Indulgence is about the good things in life. In an indulgent culture it is good to be free. Doing what your impulses want you to do, is good. Friends are important and life makes sense. In a restrained culture, the feeling is that life is hard, and duty, not freedom, is the normal state of being” – larger number, larger number, indulgent</p> <p>More details on the different cultural dimension can be found in Hofstede (2001), Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) or Geert Hofstede’s website, https://geerthofstede.com/culture-geert-hofstede-gert-jan-hofstede/6d-model-of-national-culture/</p>	
Regions	Dummy variables for the 3 different regions with sextortion data from the GCB. These regions are Latin America and the Caribbean	Transparency International’s Global Corruption

	(LAC), Asia, and Europe (EU).	Barometer LAC – 2019 GCB Asia – 2020 GCB EU – 2021 GCB
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Table A3. The Phrasing of Sextortion Questions in the Different Regions – EU, Asia, and
LAC

The questions about sextortion vary somewhat in different regions but all refer to an abuse of power exercised by someone in a position of authority to extract sexual favours. In most cases, the surveys give us measures both of experiences of sextortion and perceptions of sextortion (as in the case of EU and LAC regions). In the case of the **EU** the questions are as follows:

- Some people experience situations in which public officials make requests of a sexual nature in exchange for a government service or benefit. How often do you think this happens in [COUNTRY]?
- Thinking about your own experience in the last 5 years, has it ever happened that an official in [COUNTRY] asked for something similar from you or from someone you know?

In the **Asian region**, the question is as follows, but the question about beliefs was not asked:

- Sextortion is a form of corruption which occurs when someone who has been entrusted with authority or power says that they will give a benefit (such as quicker service, approval of documents, a job or promotion or opportunity, better grades, or avoiding a fine or imprisonment) in exchange for sexual favours such as sexual activity, inappropriate touching, exposing body parts, or posing for sexual photos. Thinking about your own experience or experiences had by people you know, how often, if at all, has a public official implied either openly or suggestively to either yourself or someone you know, that they will grant a government benefit in exchange for sexual favours?

Finally, in the **LAC region** the questions were very similar to the Asia question but explicitly

refer to “public officials” and “government benefits” rather than “someone who has been entrusted with authority or power” and “benefits”, and it also includes questions about belief like in the EU.

- Sextortion is a form of corruption which occurs when a public official says that they will give a government benefit (such as quicker service, approval of documents, a job or promotion, or avoiding a fine or imprisonment) in exchange for sexual favours such as sexual activity, inappropriate touching, exposing body parts, or posing for sexual photos. How often, if at all, do you think that this occurs in this country? Do you think it happens...?
- And thinking about your own experience or experiences had by people you know, how often, if at all, has a public official implied either openly or suggestively to either yourself or someone you know, that they will grant a government benefit in exchange for sexual favours?